

1 **A circulating tumor cell in metastatic breast cancer.**

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6 We describe transcriptional qualities of the circulating tumor cell in humans with breast cancer.

7 Developmentally associated genes functioning in cell polarity were activated, including *MPDZ*, *vangle* and
8 *prickle*. Specific cadherin genes, including *PCDH19* and *CDH18* were induced in the CTC isolated from
9 human circulation concomitant with induction of *zyxin* and *vimentin*, validating a role for cadherins in the
10 epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). A molecule with lesser described functions in cancer metastasis,
11 *JHY* with functions in ciliogenesis was differentially expressed. A suite of transcription factors from the *KLF*
12 and *T-box* family were transcriptionally activated in circulation. These details are among the first systems-level
13 description of the CTC in humans with cancer. Importantly, the kinase *ALK* was activated in CTC obtained
14 from the periphery, revealing a critical therapeutic vulnerability in metastatic breast cancer.
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